

MEDIATIZED EU - Mediatized Discourses on Europeanization and Their Representations in Public Perceptions

Research Summaries: Historical Overview

This series of summaries presents the results of different phases of research of MEDIATIZED EU, grouping all seven case-studies. The present issue summarises results of desk research, with a longitudinal overview of the available academic literature, policy developments and available data on the transformations of media discourses, elite views and public opinions of the EU and Europeanisation in each of the project countries. This research phase also identifies key trends that inform the stage of media analysis, covered in the next issue of the summaries.

BELGIUM

In this first research stage of the MEDIATIZED EU, the Belgian desk research provides a thorough analysis of how the EU and the European Project are portrayed in Belgian media by looking at existing sources for the period of 2000 to 2021. The study primarily examines shifts in perspectives on European integration and how media platforms, political figures, and the general public frame pragmatic and identity factors. Specifically, pivotal moments in recent European history, including the 2003-2004 Eastern Enlargement, the 2008-2009 Economic Crisis, the 2014-2016 Migration Crisis, and the 2019-2020 COVID-19 Pandemic Crisis were examined. By scrutinising these significant dates and crisis events, the research aims to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how the EU and the European Project are depicted and perceived within the Belgian media.

Specifically, the study addresses how the Belgian media has portrayed the European project over the last twenty years and transmitted the discourses to the public, examines the methods employed by media and political elites to set or influence the agenda, and explores whether new and old media represent socio-economic realities, utilise identity and practical arguments and whether they develop changing or static representations over time and crises. The historical

overview first delves into the complex media landscape of Belgium to set the context by primarily focusing on Wallonia and Flanders and their changing media landscape as a result of regional and linguistic division, freedom levels, ownership, and political party structures. Following the examination of the unique media environment of Belgium, it examines the available sources focusing on discourses and media representations of the EU between 2000 and 2021 over the four crisis periods mentioned above. Lastly, it also addresses anti-EU myths in the Belgian media for the same period and cyber strategy and strategy against disinformation in Belgium.

Documents reviewed

The historical overview delves into multiple sources including all types of mass media journalism, surveys, media articles, policy papers, and scholarly works to explore the concept of 'Europeanisation' as perceived by different stakeholders such as the political elite, media, and the general public. The selection process included a multivariate approach, utilising keywords and consulting with academics and media experts. The aim was to gather sources in English, French, and Dutch, providing a comprehensive view of Belgian media narratives during the aforementioned crises. A total of 110 articles and studies were reviewed, drawing primarily from academic research and media articles, but also polling studies and raw data. The distribution of sources across the identified crises was equitable, except for the 2003-2004 period, reflecting the differing levels of attention paid to enlargement within existing and newly entered EU countries.

Highlights and trends

The desk research report highlights significant trends related to structural-material factors in Belgian media. One major trend is the commercialisation, privatisation, and sensationalization of media over the past two decades, observed in both Flanders and Wallonia but progressing more rapidly and liberally in Flanders. This acceleration is attributed to varying laws and informal coordination between regions. Unlike Wallonia, where trade unions and political party funding have influenced media agendas, Flanders prioritises viewership ratings over substantive journalism, leading to higher levels of populism, myths, and openness to unfiltered anti-EU narratives during crises. These trends are influenced by ownership and party structures, as well as linguistic-cultural traditions across Belgium.

When it comes to the disadvantages and advantages of EU membership, it is important to note that disadvantages attributed to membership in Belgian media are typically discussed from practical, economic, and sensational viewpoints. Criticisms often revolve around economic, migration, health policy, democracy, and sovereignty concerns, reflecting a pragmatic approach. However, anti-EU sentiments and drawbacks remain prevalent in the media, evolving from practical critiques to more sensational and politicised arguments, particularly during crises like the migration crisis. The narrative shifts from pragmatic discussions to identity-based narratives over time, especially in Flanders, with increased emphasis on issues related to national sovereignty,

culture, religion, and EU interference in national affairs. This shift is driven by identity politics and is intertwined with the rise of anti-EU political parties and identity-based arguments.

The framing and agenda-setting in the media are influenced by political party systems, competition within media landscapes, viewership ratings, and the impact of social media. Overall, the portrayal of EU disadvantages evolves from pragmatic to identity-based narratives, shaped by various factors within the media landscape. Lastly, the analysis highlights a notable increase in EU myths and disinformation, particularly since the migration crisis and even more so during the COVID-19 crisis. Before the migration crisis, myths were primarily propagated by the media, whereas in the past five years, they have been more associated with political parties, the general public, and unidentified online sources.

There is a clear shift in myth dissemination linked to the migration and COVID-19 crises, likely influenced by media sensationalism, commercialisation, regional divisions in Belgium, and the expansion of content-producing platforms for non-traditional media online. New anti-EU myths often stem from citizen concerns and are more bottom-up compared to previous years. Both crises also witnessed an increase in conspiratorial and identitarian anti-EU myths, paralleled by a rise in anti-elite sentiments and decreased trust in politicians. This trend peaked during the 2014-2016 migration crisis, affecting both online and offline Belgian media.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

Analysing the perception of Europeanisation in Belgium is vital due to ongoing shifts in media narratives and public discourse related to the EU, particularly amidst various crises and their implications. The existing literature underscores the need for further research to gauge the evolution of negative EU media narratives from pragmatic to identity-driven concepts. It also highlights the importance of considering underlying factors like ownership, media freedom, and commercialisation, especially when comparing Flanders and Wallonia, to gain a comprehensive understanding of the emerging media discourse trajectories in which the Belgian team structured its next reports on them.

 ESTONIA

The Estonian media landscape has generally been diverse, with a lot of media outlets appearing after the restoration of independent statehood in 1991 or even before, starting from printed media, moving to a diversification and multiplication also of broadcast media, recently moving primarily online.

Digital media play an important role in Estonia and are used by a broad section of the society. This includes public and commercial online media sources as well as social media, domestic and international. Estonia was one of the first countries in the world to have a cybersecurity strategy. However this did not deal with media content specifically.

The research covers the period from 2003 to 2021 and analyses the Estonian path towards European integration since the Estonian accession to EU up to the COVID-19 pandemics. The goal was to examine how media has influenced the public opinion and narrative-building on Europeanisation during the process of integration. Five milestones have been established. The first milestone is set to the years 2003-2004, when Estonia joined the European Union. Immediately after the accession, Estonia faced the economic boom, which ended with the emergence of the global economic crisis at the end of 2007. The second milestone refers to the years 2007-2009, just before Estonia joined the Eurozone. Europe was at the dawn of the economic crisis, but Estonia became a target of Russia's aggressive ambitions characterised by the Bronze soldier crisis in Tallinn in 2007 and Russia's aggression against Georgia the year after that. The next milestone is set by the migration crisis of 2014-2016, which strongly influenced public opinion and political processes. During this period, the populist wave reached Estonia and strengthened Eurosceptic views in the country. The last milestone of 2020-2021 marks the crisis produced by the spread of Coronavirus and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Documents reviewed

The analysis is based on public surveys and media research analysis, made by experts during the period from 2003 to 2021. Estonian media monitoring enterprises (e.g. Saar Poll OÜ, Kantar Emor, Turuuuringute AS) have conducted surveys on a regular basis, which measure the media consumption of Estonian residents. In addition the EU surveys (e.g. Eurobarometer) provided valuable information for this research.

Several other surveys have also been included in this research. GLOBSEC's report "Voices of Central and Eastern Europe: Perceptions of democracy & governance in 10 EU countries", provides an insight into democratisation and governance systems in 10 Central and Eastern European countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania and Slovakia, which reveals that the social understandings of the Estonian population tend to be more similar (more conservative) to Central-and Eastern European countries than to Nordic or Western-European ones, which is confirmed by our research. At the request of the Ministry of Defence, there have been regular surveys among Estonian residents on defence and security issues since 2001, which also examine EU contribution to national defence and security-related discourses.

Highlights and trends

Several factors characterise the Estonian integration process throughout the period. First, there has always been a more Eurosceptic or even isolationist side of society, which has been quite invisible for a long time, but became more organised with the European populist wave of 2010s, which simultaneously brought political success. Second, a Russophone community in Estonia and their integration problems have been a long-time concern in Estonian political discourses. Both communities have been separated from each other since the Soviet period and the Russophone community often shares different values than the Estonian community. Third, security factors, related to the indirect security guarantees Estonia expected to achieve through EU accession, have also played an important role, in particular through reducing potential political and economic influence of the Russian Federation on Estonia. Especially in the first years after EU accession, the potential security guarantees have motivated the majority of the public to support the accession.

There has been consistent support concerning approximately two thirds of the population for EU membership in Estonia over the years after the referendum about accession, and the level of support has not changed significantly over the years. The process of Europeanisation and the acceptance of European values has been a more painful process. A strong ideological gap in society appeared in the second decade of the 21st century, and the conservative trend has received significant support in Central and Eastern Europe. The Eurosceptic side of the society comprises the ethno-nationalist political community of around one third of the population and about 20% are vocal opponents of the European Union, which mainly concerns supporters of the Estonian Conservative People's Party (EKRE).

The potential EU security guarantees dominated popular opinion in the first decade of 2000s, but their role in later years has not been as significant. Estonia has a lot of experience of being targeted by Russian disinformation as well as cyberattacks and thus it has been more rigorous and holistic than some other European countries with less overt confrontation with Russia.

In general, disinformation campaigns in Europe often involve subjects linked to the EU and its policies, exploiting issues such as the economic and migratory crises, the rise of populism and Brexit. Estonia is targeted by Russian disinformation via Russian media as well as by social media "trolls" and similar, but a good awareness in society to some extent can help to mitigate the effects.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

The Mediatized EU research focused on three different political communities: mainstream community, which is overwhelmingly pro-European, the Russophone community, which was under the influence of the media space of Russian Federation for a long time, and the ethno-nationalist community, which is strongly Eurosceptic. The Russophone community has been more supportive

of the EU than of NATO membership. The research found that discourses related to the European Union may have essential influence on public opinion, but the knowledge of EU's policies remains rather limited and does not affect the media discourses. The EU issues remain external for the big part of the general public audience, and are not recognised as "our issues", which to some extent creates a potential source for Euroscepticism. The support for EU membership has grown during the crises (riots of 2007, pandemics), but there have also been issues that have strengthened Eurosceptic voices (immigration, LGBT issues).

GEORGIA

At the initial stage of project implementation, the Georgian team provided an overview of available academic literature, policy developments, and existing data related to the transformations of media discourses, elite views, and public opinions on the EU and Europeanisation. Taking into account the elite-media-public triangle, the desk research aimed to analyse the representation of the EU and European integration in Georgian media, exploring how media discourses either support or hinder the European project and how they resonate in Georgian public opinion.

The scholarly literature highlights two key factors influencing public opinion and political action towards the European project and Europeanisation: pragmatic considerations linked to gains and losses from Europeanisation and identity concerns related to cultural threats. Therefore, the historical overview focuses on the representations of pragmatic and identity considerations in the media, elite, and popular perceptions. The overview commences by establishing the context for the analysis of Georgian media discourses on the EU and Europeanisation. This involves outlining the media landscape, discussing media polarisation resulting from political polarisation, examining the media freedom index, and exploring the growing populist rhetoric in the Georgian media.

Following the contextualization, the relevant literature has been discussed, focusing on the anti-Western/anti-European rhetoric in the Georgian-language media and encompassing identity and pragmatic factors related to European integration. Subsequently, the perceptions and discourses of Georgian political elites regarding the EU and Europeanisation have been explored and evaluated in the light of above mentioned factors. This is followed by an examination of the attitudes of the Georgian population toward the EU and European integration.

Documents reviewed

Systematic reporting on the media representations of the EU and Georgia's European integration has been available since 2014, marked by Georgia's signing of the EU association agreement. This reporting is primarily derived from the works of non-governmental organisations, including the Media Development Foundation (MDF), Georgian Institute of Politics (GIP), Georgia's Reforms

Associates (GRASS), and the Georgian Foundation for Strategic and International Studies (GFSIS). Regarding the analysis of popular perceptions of the EU and Georgia's Europeanisation, quantitative data is accessible through the Caucasus Research Resource Center's (CRRC Georgia) biennial nationwide surveys on "Knowledge about and Attitudes toward the EU in Georgia" (2009-2019). Additionally, qualitative data is available from focus group discussions with populations of various age groups in the capital and major cities of Eastern and Western Georgia, conducted by the Center for Social Sciences (CSS) after both the signing of the EU-Georgia association agreement (2014-2016) and the enactment of visa-free travel (2018-2020). The overview of elite discourses also relies on the data derived from the abovementioned studies implemented by the CSS team.

Highlights and trends

The analysis of available research and data brings to the forefront the significant political polarisation within the country, which permeates into the media landscape, where various channels, including TV, print, and online platforms, are employed to advance the interests of different political entities. The influence of political actors on editorial policies contributes to a polarised media environment, further exacerbated by the widespread dissemination of Russian state-supported anti-Western/anti-European propaganda through traditional and online media.

The Georgian government lacks a well-defined strategy to counter this challenge. Consequently, anti-Western/anti-European disinformation campaigns have become notably prevalent, with instances of propaganda rising significantly over the past 5-6 years. Anti-European messages primarily focus on the perceived threats to national identity as well as losses vs gains related to Georgia's European integration. Identity threats are linked to the perceptions of the EU imposing non-traditional family values, portraying Russia positively as a safeguard against the Western "moral occupation."

In terms of pragmatic considerations, the main losses are depicted in economic and security terms, portraying the EU as unsupportive and ineffective compared to Russia. Anti-European media discourses centre around the dichotomy of the EU versus Russia in terms of threats versus salvation. The elite and popular views of Georgia's Europeanisation echo similar identity and pragmatic considerations. However, unlike the anti-European media narratives, political elites express predominantly optimistic views. They are optimistic about Georgia's reunification with its "European family" and they highlight the EU's role in safeguarding Georgia against Russia's imperialistic ambitions. Additionally, political elites anticipate positive economic outcomes resulting from the country's integration with the EU.

It is significant to note that public views align closely with elite perspectives, revealing a prevailing sentiment of "pragmatic Euro-optimism" among the Georgian populace. This indicates widespread expectations of various benefits from the Europeanisation process, particularly, the ultimate goal

of EU membership. Despite an optimistic stance among political elites regarding Georgia's Europeanisation, certain ambivalence is evident in both political and public perceptions. This reflects what Kelstrup calls the integration dilemma, common in small states like Georgia, balancing participation in the integration process while preserving national sovereignty and identity. Anti-European media outlets manipulate these sentiments, focusing on power asymmetry or potential losses. Coordinated efforts among political actors, media, and civil society are crucial to ensure a cohesive representation of the EU and Georgia's Europeanisation consistent with the country's foreign policy objectives.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

Tracing Georgia's historical path towards European integration and the challenges encountered on this way is of utmost importance, as it showcases how a country might transform from what Smith calls Russia's privileged sphere of influence to the aspirant one that has been granted the EU's candidate status. Georgia's case might serve as a vivid example of how the EaP countries might experience Europeanisation and what internal (such as democratic deficit) and external (such as Russia's intrusion in their foreign policy aspirations using hard, soft and sharp power) obstacles they might face in this process. Thus, based on the example of Georgia, this report contributes to a deeper analysis of the undercurrents taking place in the EU's Eastern neighbourhood and provides EU policy makers with the necessary context to better understand these countries' political, public and media landscapes.

HUNGARY

The observation period extends over the 2000-2020 years with a brief overview of the first post-transition decade. The political consolidation and the democratisation process consensually supported that Hungary should be part of the EU. This context suffered fundamental blows due to internal and external reasons. These changes became consequential on the EU related discourses. In terms of the elite, the left-right political balance was replaced by the dominance of the right, embodied by consecutive Fidesz governments since after 2010. The conservative side began to acquire populist traits and to stabilise its position it began to build on nationalism and as part of it created and fostered anti-EU sentiments. This contributed to increased and affective polarisation among the public: although the pro-EU sentiments did not decline, they acquired a more pragmatic turn in harmony with the populist government views. The populist turn undermined the media landscape, the government media became dominant and misinformation or fake news reached out for the evaluation of the EU in these organs.

Documents reviewed

Desk research had three major sources to rely upon. First, academic interest tended to be high regarding elite and public attitudes towards European integration due to the lasting controversies between left and right political forces, a tendency that further increased after 2010 with the landslide victory of the populist right. Second, the desk research used a large number of evidence-based sources, among others INTUNE (2007, 2009) and ENEC (2014) projects and the 2014 Voter Study of the European Election Study (EES) for the general public as well as Eurobarometer surveys. Third, the desk research built on the findings of Hungarian think tanks (research institutes) that published their data and results about the EU context of Hungarian politics.

Highlights and trends

Against the background of failed democratisation when the media got under government surveillance and government anti-EU stances dominate discourse within the identity discourse the nativist components gathered ground. Public service media has become the primary tool of propaganda. The global economic crisis and particularly the migration crisis resulted in a significant shift in the politicians' public discourses about the EU mainly strengthening the sovereigntist discourse. Hungarian public support of the integration was also mainly in decline until 2012, when public support started to increase again. Nevertheless, the Hungarian public opinion remained less polarised in terms of support for the EU than that of its political elite. Also, public attitudes while showing fluctuation do not reflect dramatic changes. In 2004 Hungary was around the EU average in terms of positive perception of the EU, it dropped below the EU average by 2012, just to increase around the average again by 2020. It seems that the government's anti-EU discourse dominance does have a reverse impact.

International literature argues that national political elites are more supportive of integration, than the population of the countries concerned. The picture is somewhat nuanced by the Hungarian data as the take-over of the populist right at the elite level challenged this observation. The elite-public discrepancy and the relative stability of the EU related attitudes among the public warns about the low level of trust in the media in Hungary. The proportion of those that trust most news most of the time is extremely low in Hungary, only 30 percent.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

The change of the political and economic context resulted in a significant shift in the politicians' public discourses about the EU. Previous pragmatic and technocratic discourses were increasingly replaced by symbolic messages about national sovereignty where the EU appeared in a negative role, often as a threat. Discourses about the EU rarely centred around Hungary being part of the EU, the EU was usually seen as an external actor. The changing EU discourse of Fidesz became the

mainstream discourse after 2010. Moreover, Fidesz in addition to establishing sovereigntist ideology seeks to create an international platform to foster this frame. More recently Russian disinformation propaganda has also found its place in government dominated media. The dominance of anti-EU discourses is a prime example of how internal political developments are interlinked with EU-related politics and discourses. This context is a warning sign that EU policymakers should pay more attention to media structures and internal discourses.

IRELAND

At the pre-fieldwork stage of project implementation, the Irish team provided an overview of relevant academic literature, policy developments, and existing data related to the transformations of media discourses, elite views, and public opinions on the EU and Europeanisation. Building on the elite-media-public triangle, the desk research analysed the representation of the EU and European integration in Irish media, exploring how media and elite discourses either support or hinder the European project and how they resonate with public opinion. The historical overview focused on the representations of pragmatic and identity considerations in the media, elite, and public perceptions, following the Foucauldian framework as the theoretical basis for analysis, which highlights these factors as key ones influencing both elite and public views of Europeanisation.

The historical overview first contextualised the scholarship on Irish media and elite discourses about the Ireland-EU relationship by mapping the Irish media landscape and providing available data on political polarisation, media's political parallelism and perceptions of media independence in Ireland. Following the contextualisation, the overview analysed the relevant literature on Irish attitudes to Europeanisation, highlighting key identity and pragmatic factors revealed over the past several decades. Scholarship on the perceptions and discourses of Irish political elites regarding the EU and Europeanisation was analysed in light of key identity and pragmatic factors. Finally, available data on attitudes of the Irish public toward the EU and European integration were examined. The overview concluded with a brief examination of relevant Irish policy developments in areas related to media freedom, media literacy, disinformation and cybersecurity.

Documents reviewed

The historical overview examined academic scholarship on Irish elite views of the relationship with the EU and key factors and events (such as referenda, the austerity crisis, Brexit, etc.) that have shaped political elite perceptions. Another branch of scholarship provided insights about media coverage of EU affairs in Ireland, Ireland's involvement in European affairs, as well as broader analyses of the Ireland-EU relationship coverage by Irish mainstream media. Yet another section of the overview dealt with survey and poll data on Irish public attitudes towards the EU (e.g., the

Eurobarometer surveys or the EMI Red C polls), as well as relevant scholarship synthesising this data with other sources of knowledge to highlight key identity and pragmatic factors influencing Irish public opinion. The overview also reviewed relevant Irish policy documents and proposals, parliamentary debates, and expert consultations to assess the scope of relevant policies and to determine areas for future policy recommendations. This provided a broad historic overview of knowledge to date about media framing, elite and public perceptions of Europeanisation in Ireland.

Highlights and trends

The historical analysis of scholarship and data on Irish public opinion, media and elite discourses on Europeanisation throughout the development of Ireland's relationship with the EU reveals a predominantly favourable disposition of Irish media, elites and public towards the EU over time, but also notes the comparatively low level of awareness of key EU affairs, especially among the public. Evidence suggests that the Irish public is guided by predominantly pragmatic considerations in shaping opinions about the EU and Europeanisation, while identity factors remain insignificant.

The Irish public sphere is heavily mediatized, yet displays little evidence of political parallelism or polarisation. Thus, media coverage of EU affairs is less prone to explicitly pro- or anti-EU framings, yet matters related to EU integration and Ireland's role in the Union are often discussed through the prism of domestic politics. Media coverage thus seeks to domesticate EU-related considerations for its Irish audience, connecting national policy issues and actors to key aspects of EU policy making and focusing on both pragmatic and identity-related outcomes of EU-level processes for Ireland.

Ireland's mainstream media tend to echo and represent the views of the Irish elites on the EU and Europeanisation. There was evidence of elite appropriation of key media discourses on Europeanisation, creating a disconnect between public concerns relating to the EU which are not always reflected in elite discourses. Irish public attitudes show a lack of interest in or knowledge about EU affairs. There is constant broad support for the EU, which generated some tension at moments of crisis or decision-making (e.g., during key referenda), when the less-informed portion of the public relied on identity considerations rather than informed pragmatism.

The "mutual benefit" frame was often promoted by the Irish elites and largely supported by the Irish media. It highlights the pragmatic benefits of EU membership and stresses Ireland's unique contribution to the EU, allowing for a positive assessment of the EU's role and minimising the threat to Irish national identity. This frame persists in elite and media discourses, however mutual benefit arguments are less successful when public attitudes are threatened by identity factors. The perception of the EU as a "reliable decision maker" in comparison to the national government has persisted in Irish public opinion, and support for the EU grew during the Brexit crisis and the

COVID-19 pandemic based on how EU's actions to protect Ireland from the fallout resonated in national elite and media discourses.

The "solidarity" frame persisted, informed by both pragmatic and identity considerations. During the migration crisis, Irish elites promoted an identity-driven discourse of solidarity, connecting it to Ireland's history of migration. The public's support for EU actions on migration was characterised by agreement on solidarity, but a lack of enthusiasm about immigration.

Support for the EU in the Irish elite-public-media triangle was reactivated during Brexit. Irish political elites regarded Brexit as a matter of both pragmatic considerations regarding trade and identity issues ensuring the continuation of the peace process. The Brexit period saw likely the highest amount of EU-related coverage in Irish media, which was overwhelmingly positive. Marginal voices agitating for an "Irexit" were drowned in the dominant positive assessments of the EU's role. Irish public attitudes supported this "mutual benefit" frame and saw notable improvement in the post-Brexit period, though displayed predominantly pragmatic concerns which the EU was seen as assisting Ireland.

The "mutual benefit" and "solidarity" frames remained strong during COVID-19, where positive views of the EU were confirmed by all parties. The pragmatic frame of the EU as a key decision maker waned, with Irish citizens positively assessing EU's supportive role, while also identifying the national government as a key decision maker, sometimes viewed in the context of Ireland's EU membership.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

Our research finds that Irish elites have engaged in "domestication" or "Hibernization" of EU affairs, including through the media coverage, and these strategies have been made possible by the relative lack of political polarisation and an overall pragmatic optimism towards EU-Ireland relations. The anti-EU/populist rhetoric has been relatively low in the Irish public sphere and mainstream media, and apart from the economic crisis, the Irish public have remained staunchly EU-positive.

While in the run-up to 2020-2021, there has been a low perceived threat of disinformation in Irish scholarship and public opinion, this has changed during the later years of the Brexit crisis and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The threat posed by disinformation in the digital public sphere is recognised, illustrated by the permeability of the Irish public to polarised or manipulative discourses online during Brexit and COVID-19. The possible risks of disinformation and populist narratives are made more acute by the consistently low level of public awareness about EU affairs, which is at odds with the EU-positive attitudes towards the EU in Ireland. This finding is especially relevant in assessing the possible risks posed by hostile actors seeking to influence the dominant

EU-related discourses in the Irish media in the run up to EU elections in 2024 and the ongoing European security crisis around Russia's invasion of Ukraine.

PORTUGAL

An in-depth and comprehensive analysis of how the Portuguese political elites, media and public opinion interact concerning Europeanisation has been mainly absent from existing academic literature. However, in a review of the existing resources, a preliminary analysis shows that there is, indeed, a close and underexplored link between the three elements in this triangle that tend to feed each other in representations of the EU and Europeanisation. After an initial period in the post-dictatorship transition (from 1974 onwards) where an anti-EU narrative was noticeable, the Portuguese political elite has been positive about EU integration, with the mainstream media and public opinion following suit.

Concerning the topics and elements that have been informing Europeanisation in Portugal, there is a prevalence of pragmatic factors, though pragmatic and identity factors cross-cut and are mutually reinforced. Democratisation, economic development and security go hand-in-hand with fundamental values underpinning democracy and human rights. Moreover, a self-identification with an Euro-Atlantic vocation that combines the European and the Atlantic vectors is visible and very much present in Portuguese political, social and media landscapes.

In order to grasp this historical process and how it has been discussed in the country, our desk research phase engaged in a historical overview of existing literature and resources covering the period between 2003 and 2021. This period encompasses relevant moments for the European Union, as identified by the MEDIATIZED EU project. These include the 2003 - 2004 Eastern Enlargement process, the 2008 - 2009 economic crisis, the 2014 - 2016 migrant crisis, and the 2020 - 2021 Covid-19 pandemic crisis. An additional overview of the period spanning from 2003 - 2020 collected information, data and debates on the Portuguese mediascape, including media regulation, ownership, the relation between media and elites, media literacy and trust, and overall media consumption patterns.

Documents reviewed

Documents reviewed include scholarly articles, articles authored by political actors and officials, policy briefs, thematic / research reports, opinion surveys, parliamentary reports, proposals and recommendations, and official documents. Much of these documents were issued by the National Defence Institute (IDN), a central service under the State's direct administration, endowed with administrative, scientific and pedagogical autonomy; the Institute of International Strategic Studies (IEEI), a think-tank founded in 1980, an important period for the country's democratisation, and closed in 2013; the Portuguese Institute of International Relations (IPRI), a research institute

founded and supported by NOVA University of Lisbon, the Luso-American Foundation for Development (FLAD) and other key foundations such as Oriente and Calouste Gulbenkian, joined by private companies and banks, and a Public Utility Institution since 2010; OberCom - the Observatory on Communication, associated with the University Institute of Lisbon, and other research centres focused on Communication; the European Affairs Committee of the Portuguese Parliament; as well as national private and public survey services and European surveys such as Parlemeter or Eurobarometer.

Highlights and trends

The review shows that the Portuguese political elites and media elites have been rather aligned in a positive approach towards EU integration, and public opinion has also been quite favourable to the process. At times of crisis, the role of the EU in Portuguese life becomes more acute, with criticism arising, but never to the extent of allowing an anti-EU narrative to really take shape. The intervention of the troika European Central Bank, European Commission and the International Monetary Fund between 2011 and 2014 gathered criticism from the left and applause from the right, with the possibility of leaving the EU being vented by left-wing opinion makers. But despite the criticisms centred on social impacts of austerity measures, once they were softened, a positive image of the EU was again widespread in dominant political and media discourses.

The European vector of Portuguese foreign policy is consistent and shows a continued commitment through the support to efforts to achieve consensus among European partners in policy options as well as the role of Portugal as a frontrunner in key issues, such as the European Monetary Union, or defence and security matters. This is also part of the strategy of re-centralising Portugal – a small country at the western edge of Europe – in EU policies.

The economic dimension of Europeanisation has always played a strong role in discussing its advantages for Portugal's integration into the EU, the surveys show, which is confirmed when looking at the triangle media-political elite-public opinion, in the prevalence of a pragmatic and even instrumental approach towards the EU, based on the benefits and advantages arising from integration. In terms of the pragmatic factors, throughout time, a new way of doing politics was very strong in the first years, when Europeanisation and democratisation were signalled as going hand-in-hand; economic development has probably been the strongest material factor; and security issues, including migration, have risen in the agenda, bringing a more nuanced approach towards Europeanisation.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

The study of the Portuguese case combines the identification and analysis of trends and evolution of the Portuguese mediascape concerning media ownership, media regulation, journalism and opinion practices, and consumption patterns. Based on research findings and opinion polls, for

instance, it examines trends, the evolution and patterns of media's representations, and public and elite perceptions of the EU itself, the European community project, and the EU concerning the selected topics. The study unpacks the triangulation between media, elites and the public regarding the Europeanisation process across time, finding there is a trend for general alignment of Portuguese foreign policy with the EU, in line with the Portuguese European vocation, strengthened after the Carnation Revolution that paved the way for democratisation and European integration. Moreover, the media give voice to this Europeanisation process, to a great extent mimicking political discourse. This does not mean, however, there are no contentious issues on the agenda, thus analysing this process from the perspective of diverse Portuguese actors, namely political parties, Parliamentarians, Governmental actors, civil society, and the different media actors, is fundamental to grasp nuances, and both supportive and critical voices. Portugal's case has already revealed interesting nuances with which the research engages and which have generated further questions for an ongoing inquiry of the country's integration into the EU.

 SPAIN

At the initial stage of our research, the Spanish team provided an overview of available academic literature, policy developments, and existing data related to the transformations of media discourses, elite views, and public opinions on the EU and Europeanisation. Taking into account the elite-media-public triangle, the desk research aimed to analyse the representation of the EU and the European integration project in Spanish media, exploring how media discourses either support or hinder the European project and how they resonate in the Spanish public opinion.

The consulted sources highlight three key factors influencing public opinion and political action towards the European project and Europeanisation: pragmatic considerations linked to gains and losses from Europeanisation (economic development, education, and proper functioning of political institutions); identity concerns stemming from European integration; and, digital factors resulting from digitalisation process and the challenges posed by disinformation to the legitimacy of democratic systems. The overview commences by establishing the context for the analysis of Spanish media discourses on the EU and Europeanisation.

This involves outlining the media landscape, discussing how media polarisation resulting from political polarisation has not resulted in a polarised coverage of the EU, and exploring why a Eurosceptic stance has emerged in some junctures in a traditionally strong pro-EU country such as Spain. Following the contextualization, the Spanish team's research focuses on the evolution of Spaniards' perceptions on the European integration process, framing by media outlets and political discourse, during the following four periods: Eastern enlargement & 20th anniversary of Spain's entry into the EU: 2004–2006; the economic/financial crisis: 2007–2009; the migrant/refugee

crisis: 2013–2016; and COVID-19 management: 2020–2021. This is followed by an assessment on the strategies adopted by both the EU and the Spanish government to tackle disinformation.

Documents reviewed

Information regarding the Spanish media landscape and media discourses and public opinion on Europeanisation in Spain was collected through myriad sources, including public opinion surveys conducted by the EU (Eurobarometer) and Spanish institutions such as the Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas (Center for Sociological Research) (CIS). The data analysis was complemented by consulting a wide array of academic literature, reports from both private (think tanks, NGOs) and public institutions (European and Spanish bodies and agencies), as well as EU and Spanish policies, regulations, and case law.

Highlights and trends

Spain has historically maintained a strong pro-European stance, yet over the last 15 years, a soft Eurosceptic sentiment has taken root, especially in the context of the Eurozone crisis. The analysis of available research and data reveals two main drivers behind this trend: first, that Euroscepticism is mainly motivated by pragmatic considerations towards external crises; and, second, that anti-European sentiments have been fueled by the use of social media and the dissemination of disinformation and fake news.

Despite the polarisation existing in the Spanish political system, there is a shared pro-European attitude among political parties in Spain. Furthermore, this political polarisation has not resulted in a polarised coverage of the EU, as media reporting has largely served as a transmission belt of dominant political discourses. Additionally, public opinion surveys consistently indicate that Spaniards feel “not very well informed” about EU issues. These trends suggest a significant “top-down” effect in shaping the Spanish pro-European position, as evidenced by the strong support that the EU Eastern Enlargement and the EU Constitution gathered in Spain in 2004. However, the advent of the 2008 economic/financial crisis initiated a current of Euroscepticism that intensified as the effects of the crisis worsened during the 2013-2016 period and again during the 2020-2021 COVID-19 pandemic. This trend shows that in Spain there is a strong correlation among negative attitudes towards the EU and external crises.

The analysis of available research and data also reveals that the intensification of the Euroscepticism current, which began in 2016, coincided with the irruption of social media and growing scepticism regarding the independence and reliability of traditional media among Spanish citizens. In this regard, studies have shown that Euroscepticism was higher among those who preferred to be informed through social media (Serrano-Puche, 2017, 434; Vara, 2017, 95). Concerns about the role of the Internet and social media disseminating misinformation and fostering Euroscepticism were further fueled by the Brexit process (2017-2019), and have

escalated during the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2021). Indeed, since 2020, Spanish media discourse on Europeanisation has focused on the increasingly harmful effects of the rise of disinformation and fake news on the European project.

The delegitimizing effects of disinformation campaigns on the European project prompted the adoption of various strategies by both the EU and the Spanish government. While the EU initiated efforts to tackle disinformation as early as 2015, the Spanish government took action in October 2020, which evidenced the importance of this matter amid the ongoing pandemic.

MEDIATIZED EU contribution

Spain's case serves as a notable example of how (soft) Euroscepticism can emerge even in a traditionally pro-European country. Although there is not a prevalent anti-EU sentiment among Spanish political parties or media outlets, the lack of a well-informed society regarding EU matters undermines the process of Europeanisation because evaluations of EU actions during crises tend to be based on pragmatic considerations rather than a deep understanding of EU policies and mechanisms. This situation hampers the ability of society to channel its discontent through legitimate criticism, leading to the proliferation of Euroscepticism discourse jeopardising ultimately the European project. Additionally, the lack of a well-informed society regarding EU matters makes European societies more vulnerable to disinformation campaigns aimed at delegitimizing the European project. This report contributes to a deeper analysis on the implications of not fostering a stronger European identity and offers EU policy makers with a better understanding of the dynamics surrounding Euroscepticism.

For more information on the project and on our results, visit us at
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